

The Tendencies of Development of the Management in the Education System of the Republic of Kazakhstan

Altynai Zhaitapova, and Aizhan Satyvaldiyeva

Abstract—In this article the authors investigate the main tendencies of development of the management in the education system of the Republic of Kazakhstan: problems, solutions and development of the education system of Kazakhstan in the realities of globalization.

Keywords—Change management, education, globalization, innovations management systems, quality of education.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE Republic of Kazakhstan, the Kazakhstan society, as a majority of countries, while choosing its own way of integration to the world community rests on the proceeding globalization processes and defines its development way by different spheres on the base of meta-system approaches and innovation technologies.

Development of the general education system is now at a new stage in our republic. Its aim is clearly described in the Development of the education system concept: "... education system should be brought into accord with requirements of Kazakhstan development" [1]. Economic growth, with a qualified and dynamic person as a main resource, requires education of a new quality. In modern conditions, educational guidelines of school have to be renewed. Knowledge oriented school should be replaced by competency oriented education which is aimed at building-up for graduates preparedness to mobilize their internal (knowledge, skill, valuables) and external (information, material, human) resources to achieve goals defined.

In Kazakhstan education system there is a clear understanding of that that although under conditions of rapid changing world and increase of information streams the fundamental subject knowledge is obligatory base, but it is not a sufficient goal of the education in conditions of globalization. The task of imparting to learners (trainees, pupil) the skills of finding, analyzing, structuring of the information by themselves and to apply it effectively for maximal self-actualization and efficient participation in the society's life is appeared as a difficult and unfeasible in fact for scientists and practitioners.

The conservativeness of the education system demonstrated by its continuing development up to-day certainly on the base

of outdated methodological base, structure and content which remains as fact-based and not oriented to train learners for competence-based, responsible and creative participation in the society.

The crisis of education is a worldwide phenomenon. The education in the world space stack in post-industrial transition but the globalization here is. The education has been faced a challenge today. The essence of this challenge is in necessity of forming of new type of thinking, new understanding of his place in the history, society and the world by man.

World forum on education [2], activities of International educational committee of XXI century under the protection of UNESCO [3], [4], [5] and others ensured education strategy over a period of the whole life in conditions of planetary interdependency and globalization.

II. MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATION SYSTEM IN KAZAKHSTAN

The aspiration of Kazakhstan to enter the world space has revealed the need in modernization of management of education system. We accept and support the opinion that 80 % of quality depends on management. So our researches provided during a number of years were devoted to introducing of the philosophy of quality, value-oriented management and innovative management models to the practice [6], [7], [8].

The management in education in our country, as in many countries, has a number of problems, various contradictions given by rapid changing realities.

The legislative acts of the Republic of Kazakhstan, long-term programs and normative documents on development of education reflect the vector of the national education that is a direction of country's integration to the realities of globalization, to the European space, to the tendencies of introducing of competence-based paradigm in education [9].

As the result of the research we have revealed some possible barriers/obstacles on the way of realization of introducing of competence-based pedagogic on the following levels of management:

- the level of province/district
- the level of the educational institution/establishment
- the level of pedagogical management

What namely interferes the modernization of education and appears as an obstacle?

On the level of province/district it is:

Authors are with Kazakh National University after Al-Farabi, Kazakhstan (e-mail: a.satyvaldiyeva@mail.ru).

- Command-administrative style of the management (“the main thing is an official authority”) with forked orientation: for higher management that is “guess — please — inform — report” but for subordinates that is “expose and reveal”, “indicate and punish”, undertaking of inspections in which the quantity of inspectors exceeds the quantity of persons being inspected, etc.

- Manipulation managers of educational institutions (determination of “elite” schools and kindergartens that never fell in the list of inspectors and are always among best ones, approval and work within traditions, domination of quantity-based evaluations over quality-based evaluations, etc.);

- The ignore of scientific principles of management that is reflected by use of ineffective methods and technical of management — written communication does not correspond to the appropriate existing Standard, the violence of the rules for conducting of the effective meetings, the orientation of activities to the events, the ignore of manager’s cycle (the problem — actions on elimination of the problem — the analyze of the result), the absence of a clear structure of the organization and voluntaristic distribution of the functional duties, the declaration of the principle “let’s live in peace and friendship” in the collective;

- The elaboration of the Development program and the plan of works in accordance of wishes and the professional level of officials in the staff;

- The low adaptation level to proceeding changes, the low level of educability, blind execution of instructions and directives, etc.

On the level of the management of educational institution:

- Command-administrative style of the management (“the main thing is an official authority”) with forked orientation: for higher management that is “guess — please — inform — report” but for subordinates that is “expose and reveal, and do not punish, but take pity and forgive”, etc.

- The accent is made to the vertical of the power in the education institution but not cooperation from up to the lowest level of hierarchy;

- The divergences between management assessment of the collective’s capacity and the real capacity of the collective;

- The orientation of the works to final result but not to the effectiveness of the process;

- The limitation of the information stream to the education institution and the illusion of that that the most informed one is a manager;

- The manipulation teachers and the forming up of intrigues and stress situations;

- The dominated use of quantity assessment methods of quality evaluation, the absence and ignore of diagnostic indicators. The conclusion are made on the linear level — the cause — the effect;

- The low level of (written, oral and contacting) communication;

- The low level of computer literacy;

- The projection of the Development Program of the Education institution with emphasize to external relation instead of own forces.

In the capacity of recommendations the following would have effect in eliminating of stated above obstacles:

- The introduce of corporative management, time-management, knowledge management;

- Organizational management of introduce of modern theories, methods and techniques of management;

- To apply the collective thinking activity for decision-making that should not be mixed by the decision-making under responsibility of the manager;

- The development of a high level of professional and social self-actualization (the skill of adaptation to proceeding changes);

- The organization of activities on the base of projects;

- The establishment of the modern management systems on the base of humanitarian technologies that would provide the value-based approach.

The change management, innovation management, project management and knowledge management should become the strategic landmark of sustainable development of modern education institution.

The innovation management on the base of transfer that is devoted to changes in the school by introducing of innovations from outside of it will let realize the qualitative education process.

The process of democratization of management ought to be taken as one of most important directions in the activities of the administration of the education institution; otherwise the institution is doomed to authoritative pressure through the subjective and objective relations. Alongside with the current work defined by plans, the organization of creative work of teachers through establishment of matrix organization of management is a main objective. Herewith the vertical and horizontal management intersect, and the hard linear-functional organizational structure combines with flexible, mobile-matrix structure when besides of stable management bodies the group of adherents, i.e. the whole pedagogical collective united by one project devoted to step-by-step realization of strategic objectives of the educational institution, is established [10].

In the period, when the velocity, speedup and success play a great role in the life, the education institutions should be flexible. Nowadays the changes happen so rapidly that the managers of education have no time to react to them by traditional methods. The changes are the only thing that will exist always. If the changes earlier were predictable and they passed by small phases, then the rates of today’s time constantly challenge managers: they should learn to be effective providers of changes. The change management consists of either applying of certain “methods” and “techniques” and the art of doing the necessary in necessary moment.

The knowledge management is considered as one of branches of quality management concept. It is oriented to

improvement of approaches to quality management within the standard ISO:9004 where the attention is focused on that, that the sustainable growth is achieved in that case if the organization is able to take the changes into account and to introduce and conduct the need innovations.

To realize strategic changes and to achieve objectives according to highest level quality standards the approach should be applied is a project-oriented approach that has collected all best management methods and became a base for organization development through the prism of the knowledge management.

The innovation project is used in the capacity of a linking thread between the strategic objectives of the education institution. In the strategy the focus at the quality of education, functioning of positions of participants of the process with exception of duplication is important. The project management is carried out in the key of knowledge management.

The knowledge appearing as a resource of the organization should fit the same requirements submitted to other resources (as material, finance, human resources), i.e. the managers should provide teachers by the need knowledge in required quantity, in necessary place, in set time, with required quality and minimal expenses.

The innovation management in the modern education institution is designed to:

- be a resource of development of a modern school with the full conformity to requirements;
- reflect the integral managerial concept of the school “change management — knowledge management — project management”;
- be based on project-oriented approach with compliance to managerial integrity.

The innovation project in the modern education institution is based on the resource that is expressed as professional, social and personal qualities of teachers that are able to provide the educational service in the level demanded by time thanks to the system of lifelong learning at the workplace which is realized in the context of modern pedagogical (personal-oriented and competence-based learning) and information-communication technologies, andragogics and quality management.

The Innovation management in the modern education institution has the following characteristics:

- *by form* – this is an innovation/experimental project with the clear goal, open in the information space and it uses the modern information technologies;
- *by content* – this is an integration of the science and the practice that establishes such an environment of lifelong learning on the base of competence-based and personal-oriented learning that encourages further development of professional, personal and social qualities of a teacher and sustainable development of the system of education as a whole;
- *by organization* – this is an open system based on organizational-activity approach that is focuses at the inter-

system knowledge and wide spectrum of forms and methods of traditional work. The binding element is a knowledge management that is co-subordinated to strategic goals of changes in the educational institution and the quality parameter of education in new conditions.

III. CONCLUSION

The globalization, as a planet phenomenon of XXI-th century, gives the constant improvement of management in all spheres that exist adequately to the realities of development of man, society and world. In this regard, the theory and the practice of management of education in our country objectively forced to develop leaning to not the outdated methodological base, as we mentioned above, but to modern theories, innovation technologies and the world-scale best practices. The reform of the education system that is proceeding in Kazakhstan in present days confirms the desire and the responsibility for integration processes to the globalized space.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ministry of education and science of the Republic of Kazakhstan, “Education development concept of the Republic of Kazakhstan till 2015”.
- [2] World forum on education. Dakar frames of actions. Education for everyone: fulfillment of our collective commitments. Dakar. Senegal. April 26-28, 2000. Paris: UNESCO, 2000, p.77.
- [3] World report on education, 1998. Teachers, pedagogic activities and new technologies. UNESCO, 1998, p. 175.
- [4] Education in countries with transition economy: development tasks. Translation from English – World Bank of reconstruction and development / World Bank, 2000, p. 151.
- [5] Materials of Central Asia forum on education, January 18-19, 2002. Almaty, Kazakhstan, UNICEF Central Asia and Republic of Kazakhstan representative office, UNESCO representative office in Central Asia, 2002.
- [6] Kulekeev Zh.A., Piven G.G., Nurguzhin M.R., Kalanova Sh.M., Padiarova I.P. Quality Management system of higher professional education. Theory and practice. Karaganda: publishing house Karaganda State Technical University, 2004, p. 356.
- [7] Zhaitapova A.A. Methodological support of tutors’ professional advancement at the stage of passing to the result oriented model of educational system. Almaty, 2004, p. 183.
- [8] Kulibayeva D.N. Methodological basis of management of professionally oriented education systems of international types of school. Dissertation of a doctor of pedagogical sciences - 13.00.01. Almaty, Kazakh University of international relations and world languages after Abylai khan, 2007, p. 307.
- [9] State Education Development Program of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2011 – 2020. Astana 2010.
- [10] Zhaitapova A.A., Rudik G.A., Beloshnichenko E.V., Satyvaldiyeva A.S. Pedagogy of the XXI century on the verge of the school. Methodical information digests. Almaty 2009, p. 302.